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Human capital value and uniqueness, human resource management practices and human resource configurations: A study of software development firms

Abstract - This paper investigates whether human capital value and uniqueness embodied in employees make variations in human resource management practices and human resource configurations that are used to manage them. In this study, human resource management practices of job design, recruitment and selection, training and development, performance appraisal, and compensation were explored. A self-administered survey questionnaire was used as the main method of data collection. A random sample of employees attached to software development firms in Sri Lanka responded. The findings led to the suggestion that the firms tend to acquire individuals with the needed skills and experience from the labour market. The premium on industry experience is very high in compensation decisions. Further, the emphasis given to promotion within is minimal. Furthermore, firms provide training for short-term productivity and emphasize continuous feedback on performance with short-term results orientation.

Keywords: Human capital value, human capital uniqueness, human resource management practices, human resource configurations, software development, software developers

I INTRODUCTION

Human capital refers to the sum of employees' skills, experience, capabilities, and tacit knowledge [1]-[3]. Human capital, like physical capital, is an input in the production process for all industries. However, like physical capital, industries vary in the amount and type of resources used [4]. Human capital-intensive industries, like software development, recognize human capital as the primary value-creating asset [2] [3] [5]. Therefore, in human capital-intensive industries, human capital accumulation, transformation, creation, management, and valuation lie at the heart of commercial survival and growth [6].

The literature also suggests that human resource management (HRM) practices and human resource (HR) configurations or clusters of HR practices vary

by the value and uniqueness of employees [7]. These differences are identified as important aspects of a firm's strategic approach to HRM [7] [8] [9]. However, investigations into such variations in HRM practices in Sri Lanka remain limited.

Against this backdrop, this paper investigates whether human capital value and uniqueness embodied in employees make variations in HRM and HR configurations that are used to manage them in software development firms in Sri Lanka. In this study, five HRM practices and four HR configurations were investigated. The five HRM practices were job design, recruitment and selection, training and development, performance appraisal, and compensation. The four HR configurations were commitment, collaboration, productivity, and compliance.

II LITERATURE REVIEW

A Human Capital Value and Uniqueness

The strategic value of human capital is referred to as its potential to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of the firm, exploit market opportunities, and/or neutralize potential threats [1]. Therefore, the literature suggests that the value of human capital has the potential to contribute to the competitive advantage of firms [7]. The value of human capital can be influenced by a multitude of sources, such as an organization's strategy and technologies.

The uniqueness of human capital, on the other hand, refers to the degree to which an employee's skills and capabilities are rare, specialized, and, in the extreme, firm-specific [1] [7]. According to Lepak and Snell [10], the degree to which human capital is unique directly impacts its potential to serve as a source of competitive advantage. Further, when human capital is difficult to duplicate or imitate by other firms, it also

provides a potential source of competitive advantage. For instance, when an employee's knowledge consists of more tacit knowledge and expertise, it enhances the uniqueness of a firm's human capital.

B Human Resource Management Practices and Human Resource Configurations

The literature identifies job design, recruitment and selection, training and development, performance appraisal, and compensation as key HRM activities relating to human capital [7] [11] - [13]. These five HRM practices were investigated in this study.

HR configurations are clusters of HRM practices that reflect a firm's strategic approach to HR [13]. Lepak and Snell [10] focused on strategic value and uniqueness of human capital as principal drivers of four types of HR configurations relating to the above HRM practices. These four types of HR configurations are commitment-based, productivity-based, compliance-based, and collaborative-based. Commitment-based HR configuration nurtures employee involvement and maximizes a firm's return on human capital investment. For that, organizations may loosely define jobs to allow for change and adaptation, invest to develop unique skills and sponsor career development programmes, structure pay systems to focus on employee learning and information sharing, and use a developmental performance appraisal system to make employees receive continued and useful feedback [10]. In the productivity-based HR configuration, firms may hire and develop skills for immediate contribution, pay a market-based wage, and focus on job performance in standardized jobs that facilitate more rapid replacement [10]. In the compliance-based HR configuration, firms may ensure worker compliance with organizational policies, systems, procedures, and outcomes [7]. Finally, in the collaborative-based HR configuration, firms would likely invest heavily in the relationship itself rather than developing human capital [7]. Further, Lepak and Snell [7] suggest that there would be a variability in the degree to which firms adhere to one or multiple HR configurations.

III METHODOLOGY

A Research Design

A self-administered survey questionnaire was used as the main method of data collection. The degree of reliance on each HRM practice was measured using the 48-item measurement construct of Lepak and Snell [7] (refer to Table 4). These are on a five-point Likert-scale ranging from 1= "strongly disagree" to 5= "strongly agree". For all measurement scales, Cronbach's alpha was examined, and Principal-components factor analysis (Varimax rotation) was conducted. Reliability statistics are shown in Table 1. As proposed by Lepak and Snell [7], for each respondent, the related HRM practices were combined to form a commitment-based, productivity-based,

compliance-based, and collaborative-based HR configuration. Data analysis was conducted using SPSS. In addition to descriptive statistics, regression analysis was used for the data analysis.

TABLE 1
Measure evaluation

Construct	Explained variation	Eigenvalue	Cronbach Alpha
Job design	68.59%	2.54	0.80
Recruitment and selection	64.99%	1.92	0.71
Training and development	67.70%	2.83	0.79
Performance appraisal	68.39%	2.87	0.81
Compensation	66.79%	2.35	0.77

B Sample

A sample of software development firms was identified from the list of Software Exporters Association that fulfil 1) a firm should employ at least 50 employees, and 2) a firm should be in operation for at least 10 years. This restriction is imposed to eliminate the firms that might not have formal HRM practices [14].

Eighteen firms met these two criteria. The total number of employees in those firms is: eight firms had fewer than 200 employees, four firms had 200 to 499 employees, two firms had 500 to 999 employees, and one firm had more than 1000 employees. With regard to the years of business operation, three firms started business operations from 1979 to 1983, five firms from 1990 to 1995, and five firms in 1996.

A random sample of employees was selected from the firms. Of the 200 self-administered questionnaires distributed, 101 responses were received. The age of the respondents ranged between 25 and 38 years (mean age = 31 years). Eighty-seven percent of the respondents had bachelor's degrees, and 13 percent of the respondents had postgraduate degrees as their highest educational qualification. Sixty-five percent of the respondents were male, while 35 percent of the respondents were female.

IV RESULTS

The study investigated whether human capital value and uniqueness make variations in HRM practices and HR configurations that are used to manage them. Therefore, the results will be presented in terms of A) value and uniqueness of human capital, B) HRM practices and HR configurations used in the industry, and C) effects of human capital value and uniqueness on HRM practices and HR configurations. Data were pre-tested for the normality of the distribution and found to be normally distributed.

A Human Capital Value and Uniqueness

Table 2 shows results relating to human capital value. A mean value of 3.91 shows a high (in a five-point Likert-scale) human capital value.

Table 3 shows results relating to human capital uniqueness. Unlike human capital value, a mean value of 3.20 shows moderate (in a five-point Likert-scale) human capital uniqueness.

TABLE 2
Human capital value

	Mean	S.D.
I have skills that are instrumental for new innovations	3.92	0.57
I believe that the work I carry out creates customer value	4.25	0.52
The work I carry out enables my firm to provide exceptional customer service.	3.99	0.79
The work I perform contributes to the development of new software product	3.64	0.95
The product /service I develop is considered the best in my industry	3.38	0.74
Customer satisfaction is one of my primary concerns.	4.36	0.69
The work I carry out is essential to maintain high-quality products/services.	4.23	0.68
Overall average - human capital value	3.91	0.50

TABLE 3
Human capital uniqueness

	Mean	S.D.
The skills and knowledge require to carry out my work are not widely available in the labour market.	3.32	0.98
If I leave the current workplace, it will be very difficult to find a replacement	2.66	0.88
Competitors find difficulties in finding people with skills/knowledge that I possess.	2.94	0.78
Employees like myself are widely considered the best in the industry.	3.18	0.74
I am, to the present level, developed through on the job experiences.	3.90	0.96
I feel like I am unique to my organization.	3.34	0.91
Overall average - human capital uniqueness	3.20	0.51

B Human Resource Management Practices and Human Resource Configurations

The results relating to HRM practices and related HR configurations are shown in Table 4 (given in the overleaf).

Table 5 shows the summary of results by HRM practices and HR configurations.

TABLE 5
HR configurations

	Mean	S.D.
HRM practices		
Job design	3.12	0.42
Recruitment and selection	3.47	0.60
Training and development	3.40	0.47
Performance appraisal	3.63	0.44
Compensation	2.80	0.40
HR configurations		
Commitment	3.30	0.38
Collaboration	3.25	0.43
Productivity	3.33	0.41
Compliance	2.71	0.39

Graphs were generated to check the distribution of HRM practices and HR configurations. Fig. 1 shows a comparison of the distribution of HRM practices. Fig. 2 shows a comparison of the distribution of HR configurations. Table 6 shows Pearson correlations between variables (given in the overleaf).

Fig. 1 HRM practices

Fig. 2 HR configurations

C Effects of Human Capital Value and Uniqueness on HRM Practices and HR Configurations

It is hypothesized that human capital value and uniqueness will predict the extent of HRM practices and HR configurations used in the industry. To test this proposition, multiple regression was used. Results are shown in Tables 7 and 8, respectively. Table 7 shows regression results for each of the HRM practices. It is evident that human capital value and uniqueness significantly predict all the HRM practices except compensation.

TABLE 4
Human resource management practices and configurations

HR practice	HR configuration	Mean	S.D.
<i>Job design: I perform a job that allows me to routinely make changes in the way I perform my job</i>	Commitment	3.26	0.91
...is designed around my individual skills	Collaboration	2.99	0.98
...is extremely simple	Compliance	2.00	0.53
...is not standardized throughout the industry	Productivity	3.03	0.88
...is well-defined	Compliance	3.34	0.92
...empowers me to make decisions	Commitment	3.63	0.77
...has a high degree of job security	Commitment	3.24	0.87
...includes a routine task	Commitment	2.90	1.14
...involves job rotation	Commitment	2.58	0.80
...requires me to participate in cross-functional teams and networks	Collaboration	3.58	0.87
<i>Recruitment and selection: The recruitment/selection process for me assesses my industry knowledge and experience</i>	Collaboration	3.32	1.15
...emphasizes promotion from within	Commitment	3.01	0.98
...emphasizes my ability to collaborate and work in teams	Collaboration	3.98	0.53
...focuses on selecting the best all-around candidate, regardless of the specific job	Commitment	3.62	0.88
...focuses on my ability to contribute to strategic objectives	Commitment	3.92	0.72
...involves screening many job candidates	Productivity	3.47	0.91
...is comprehensive	Productivity	3.69	0.95
...places priority on my potential to learn	Commitment	3.82	0.89
...uses many different recruiting sources	Productivity	3.28	1.06
<i>Training and development: Training and development activities for me is comprehensive</i>	Commitment	3.60	0.85
...is continuous	Commitment	3.32	0.96
...emphasizes improving current job performance	Productivity	3.88	0.70
...emphasizes on the job experiences	Productivity	3.53	0.87
...focuses on compliance with rules, regulations, and procedures	Compliance	3.74	0.69
...focuses on team building and interpersonal relations	Collaboration	2.85	0.89
...requires extensive investments of time/money	Commitment	2.64	0.88
...seeks to increase long-term productivity	Productivity	3.30	0.86
...strives to develop firm-specific skills/knowledge	Commitment	3.77	0.87
<i>Performance appraisal: Performance appraisal for me is based on input from multiple sources</i>	Commitment	3.49	0.95
...is based on objective, quantifiable results	Productivity	3.09	0.95
...is based on team performance	Collaboration	3.38	0.95
...assesses compliance with preset behaviours, procedures, and standards	Compliance	3.28	0.78
... assesses quality of output	Productivity	3.96	0.71
...assesses quantity of output	Productivity	3.46	0.77
...emphasizes learning	Commitment	3.64	0.70
...focuses on my ability to work with others	Collaboration	3.85	0.59
...focuses on my contribution to our strategic objectives	Commitment	3.62	0.68
...includes developmental feedback	Commitment	3.99	0.75
... measures productivity and efficiency	Productivity	3.83	0.71
<i>Compensation: Compensation/rewards for me is based on straight salary</i>	Productivity	3.78	0.93
...is based on the market wage	Productivity	2.00	0.71
...is designed to ensure equity with peers	Productivity	3.13	0.77
...focuses primarily on my long-term performance	Compliance	2.72	0.83
...have a group-based incentive component	Collaboration	2.48	1.03
...have an individual incentive component	Productivity	3.78	0.93
...includes an extensive benefits package	Commitment	2.30	0.87
...places a premium on my industry experience	Collaboration	3.04	0.89
...values seniority	Productivity	2.98	0.95

TABLE 6
Correlations

		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1	Job design	1									
2	Recruitment & selection	0.28**	1								
3	T&D	0.37**	0.32**	1							
4	Performance appraisal	0.33**	0.30**	0.23*	1						
5	Compensation	0.21*	0.32**	0.04	0.16	1					
6	Commitment	0.39**	0.37**	0.38**	0.53**	0.30**	1				
7	Collaboration	0.43**	0.52**	0.20	0.59**	0.38**	0.52**	1			
8	Productivity	0.12	0.61**	0.13	0.56**	0.35**	0.60**	.52**	1		
9	Compliance	0.12	0.14	0.13	0.07	0.21	0.24*	.07	0.44**	1	
10	HC value	0.22*	0.14	0.05	0.16	0.17	0.09	.31**	0.07	0.20	1
11	HC uniqueness	0.08	0.10	0.13	0.05	0.15	0.29**	.14	0.10	0.08	0.33**

** Significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). * Significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

TABLE 7
Regression- HRM practices

	Job design (β)	Recruitment & selection (β)	T&D (β)	Performance appraisal (β)	Compensation (β)
Value	0.36**	0.34**	0.32**	0.37**	0.16
Uniqueness	0.04	0.21*	0.25*	0.06	0.10
R ²	0.12	0.16	0.11	0.13	0.04
F	8.04**	5.68**	5.56**	6.38**	1.95

*p<0.5, ** p<0.1

Table 8 shows regression results for each of the HR configurations. It is evident that human capital value and uniqueness significantly predict commitment and collaboration-based HR configurations.

TABLE 8
Regression- HR configurations

	Commitment (β)	Collaboration (β)	Productivity (β)	Compliance (β)
Value	0.18	0.36**	0.14	0.09
Uniqueness	0.23*	0.09	0.06	0.11
R ²	0.11	0.13	0.03	0.01
F	5.42**	6.57**	1.28	.621

*p<0.5, ** p<0.1

V CONCLUSIONS AND IMPLICATIONS

When employing personnel, firms can either recruit new staff from externally or develop and promote existing staff. These two approaches to employment incur various costs. For example, the former approach incurs hiring costs, and the latter triggers training and development costs. Between these two alternatives, firms choose the most efficient alternative or combination by comparing all relevant costs [2] [9]. The findings led to the suggestion that the software development firms tend to give priority to industry knowledge and experience, and tend to acquire individuals who already possess the needed skills and experience from the employment market.

Training and development activities provided by the firms imply that they emphasize training for short-term productivity. The literature suggests that firms make comparisons of the potential future benefits of human capital in making training and development decisions. In this regard, one could argue that knowledge workers today have a much shorter cycle before their skills become obsolete [15]. However, the evidence from the Sri Lankan context reveals that employers rely on new recruits [16]. Hence, prior to entering the labour market, higher education institutions should develop competencies of undergraduates [17] [18]. Overall, this finding of the study implies that employers do not expect long-term employee commitment. Therefore, software development firms are more likely to rely on short-term technical training and knowledge build-up for employees. On the other hand, irrespective of the job category, the software development firms emphasize continuous feedback on performance with a short-term results orientation.

Further, the findings led to the suggestion that software development firms mostly rely on compensation based on market wages and take steps to ensure equity with peers. The individual-based incentive component is

highly emphasized, while there is a lower concern over the team-based component. Overall, the findings on compensation practices led to the implication that the firms are more likely to acquire generic human capital externally by paying market wages and focusing on near-term productivity targets for all employees, irrespective of their job category. The findings also led to the suggestion that firms do not value seniority irrespective of their job category, and the premium on industry experience is very high in compensation decisions.

Firms use a combination of productivity-based, commitment-based, compliance-based, and collaborative-based HR configurations to manage employees. Reliance on productivity-based is the highest while reliance on compliance-based is the lowest (refer to Table 5).

With regard to the effects of human capital value and uniqueness on the HRM practices, human capital value significantly positively predicts the HRM practices of job design, recruitment and selection, training and development, and performance appraisal. Human capital uniqueness significantly positively predicts the HRM practices of recruitment and selection, training and development. However, human capital value or uniqueness had not predicted the HRM practice of compensation (refer to Table 7).

With regard to the effects of human capital value and uniqueness on HR configurations, human capital value significantly positively predicts collaboration-based strategy while human capital uniqueness significantly positively predicts commitment-based strategy. However, productivity-based and compliance-based strategies were not predicted by either human capital value or uniqueness (refer to Table 8).

Overall, the findings imply that the nature of the software development sector itself may be working as a constraint in the Sri Lankan context. This may be because the issues of addressing economic growth and industrialization led government strategies to attract foreign investment and modern technology. This has resulted in extensive opportunities for the software development firms. However, a feature of offshore outsourced services is that foreign clients of the Sri Lankan software development firms are in a continuous search for low-cost locations. In the present competitive global environment, the availability of sufficient infrastructure and skilled human resources at a lower cost has led them to offshore outsource various IT work. Hence, foreign clients of the software development firms could make this sector a highly mobile business sector. Therefore, one could argue that the Sri Lankan software development firms' preferred people management practices have been tailored to meet business objectives conditioned by the global competitive environment.

When discussing the data presented in Table 4, it is evident that software development firms choose to employ personnel in the most efficient manner. Firms prefer to hire employees, give them predetermined

tasks, focus on their short-term job performance with short-term productivity targets, and pay them market-based wages with concerns over internal equity. Further, the software development firms are likely to standardize jobs to facilitate rapid replacement, considering employees as “short timers”, irrespective of their job category. Further, the findings suggest that the specific nature of the jobs in the software development firms may not require any firm-specific skills, and they are able to make a contribution to the firms while possessing skills that are widely transferable. The preference for job-specific experience and the demand for employees create an environment for them to hop from one workplace to another and maximize their employability. This may give them a feeling that their experience is rewarded.

When comparing the HRM practices used in the software development firms, the lack of integration among these practices could be identified. In the recruitment and selection, the firms sought the ability to work in teams. The job design practices reveal that firms require employees to participate in cross-functional teams and networks. In the performance evaluations, the ability to work in teams and team performance are emphasized. However, in the training and development, the emphasis given to team building and interpersonal relations is remarkably low. Further, in compensating employees, the group-based incentive component is less emphasized. However, the literature identifies that the knowledge work should focus on groups and projects and should use the strength of the collective mind. Therefore, in providing training and development opportunities and remuneration, firms have to recognize the importance of teamwork, interdependencies between individuals, and the context where value is created.

Therefore, findings of the study imply that the HRM practices are less likely to be treated as a set of integrated practices by the software development firms. However, this should be investigated in depth in future studies.

VI LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

This study was conducted on a small scale. The study was confined to investigate five HRM practices, namely job design, recruitment and selection, training and development, performance appraisal, and compensation. The data were analysed using multiple linear regression, which has certain limitations in analysing data. Further, sample selection was confined to the software development firms. Furthermore, as an initial attempt, the study did not explore whether individual differences in terms of tenure and gender influence individuals’ perceptions of the HRM practices and HR configurations.

REFERENCES

[1] J. Barney, “Firm resources and sustained competitive advantage,” *J. of Mgt.*, Vol. 17, pp. 99–129, 1991

- [2] H. M. Chen, K. J. Lin, “The measurement of human capital and its effects on the analysis of financial statements,” *Intl. J. of Mgt.*, Vol. 20, pp. 470-478, 2003
- [3] A. Seleim, A. Ashour, N. Bontis, “Human capital and organizational performance: a study of Egyptian software companies”, *Mgt. Decision*, Vol. 45, pp. 789-801, 2007
- [4] R. W. Coff, “Human capital, shared expertise, and the likelihood of impasse in corporate acquisitions,” *J. of Mgt.*, Vol. 28, pp. 107-117, 2002
- [5] M. Gebauer, “Information systems on human capital in service sector organizations,” *New Library World*, Vol. 104, 33-41, 2003
- [6] P. O’Regan, T. Kennedy, D. O’Donnell, N. Bontis, P. Cleary, *Exploring Intellectual Capital Practice in the Irish ICT Sector*, UK: The Chartered Institute of Management Accountants, 2003
- [7] D. P. Lepak, S. A. Snell, “Examining the human resource architecture: the relationships among human capital, employment, and human resource configurations,” *J. of Mgt.*, Vol. 28, pp. 517-543, 2002
- [8] S. C. Kang, S. S. Morris, S. A. Snell, “Relational archetypes, organizational learning, and value creation: extending the human resource architecture,” *Academy of Mgt. Rev.* Vol. 32, pp. 236–256, 2007
- [9] K. J. Lin, M. L. Wang, “The classification of human capital according to the strategic goals of firms: an analysis,” *Intl. J. of Mgt.* Vol. 22, pp. 62-70, 2005
- [10] D. P. Lepak, S. A. Snell, “The human resource architecture: toward a theory of human capital allocation and development,” *Academy of Mgt. Rev.* Vol. 24, pp. 31–48, 1999
- [11] H. M. Chen, K. J. Lin, “The role of human capital cost in accounting,” *J. of Intellectual Capital*, Vol. 5, pp. 116-130, 2004
- [12] G. Z. D Huang, M. H. Roy, Z. U. Ahmed, J. S. T.Heng, J. H. M. Lim, “Benchmarking the human capital strategies of MNCs in Singapore,” *Benchmarking: An Intl. J.* Vol. 9, pp. 357-373, 2002
- [13] R. Miles, C.C. Snow, “Designing strategic human resource systems,” *Organizational Dynamics*, Vol. 13, pp. 36–52, 1984
- [14] M. A. Huselid, B. E. Becker, “Methodological issues in cross-sectional and panel estimates of the HR-firm performance link,” *Industrial Relations*, Vol. 35, pp. 400–422, 1996
- [15] L. Edvinsson, J. Camp, “Intelligent remuneration in the knowledge economy for growth of intellectual capital,” *J.I of Human Resource Costing and Accounting*, Vol. 9, pp. 112-122, 2005
- [16] V. Wickramasinghe, “Valuation of human capital by the private sector firms in the service industry in Sri Lanka,” *Intl Conf on Business Management* 6. 2009. <https://journals.sjp.ac.lk/index.php/icbm/article/view/873>
- [17] T.M. Seneviratne, V. Wickramasinghe, (2009). Information literacy skills of undergraduates of the Faculty of Architecture, University of Moratuwa. *Proceedings of 3rd Research Conference of the Faculty of Architecture Research Unit*, pp. 2-3, Faculty of Architecture, University of Moratuwa, Sri Lanka, December 18. <https://uom.lk/foa/faru/previous-faru-conferences>
- [18] T.M. Seneviratne, V. Wickramasinghe, (2009). A study of information literacy skills of Engineering undergraduates at the University of Moratuwa. In *Symposium of Engineering Research Unit*, University of Moratuwa, Sri Lanka.